

NEW PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING FOREIGN
LANGUAGES

Yakubova Dilobar Nasritdin qizi

2st year masters` student,

Master`s degree Department of English in UzSWLU

Scientific advisor: **Shukurova Zumrad**

Toshkent, Uzbekistan

E- mail: dilobaryak@gmail.com

Mobile phone: +998337016797

Annotation. This article deals with the problem of finding new techniques and ways to increase motivation for learning foreign languages. One of these forms is new pedagogical technologies, the introduction of which contributes to the effective learning of the language. The article defines the concepts of “Pedagogical technology” and “Smart education”, which are capable of providing a high level of education that meets the challenges and opportunities of today's world, will allow young people to adapt in a rapidly changing, unstable environment, and will ensure the transition from book content to active content with the help of a single common repository of educational materials in the presence of an analytical search system.

Key words: new information technologies, pedagogical technology, independent work, linguistic social networks.

In recent years, great changes have taken place in teacher education, which cover almost all aspects of the educational process. Increasingly, the question of the use of modern pedagogical technologies in teaching foreign languages is being raised. New methods and forms of teaching are emerging, which, in turn, represent not only various technologies for the means of exchanging and transmitting information through which the educational process is carried out, but also one large system of teaching methods aimed at developing the communicative knowledge of students, improving speech skills. The main task of a foreign language is to teach

practical mastery of a foreign language, to form basic knowledge, that is, the ability to carry out foreign and international communication with native speakers. The search for new pedagogical technologies is associated with a lack of motivation among students to learn a foreign language. Very often, there is no positive motivation, because when learning a foreign language, students encounter some difficulties and do not learn the material due to their psychological characteristics. Work experience shows that the use of various, modern, fresh sources and means provokes students' interest, increases their motivation for learning.

Pedagogical technology is a set of techniques, an area of pedagogical knowledge that reflects the characteristics of the deep processes of pedagogical activity, the features of their interaction, the management of which ensures the necessary efficiency of the educational process.

The use of modern pedagogical technologies in the process of teaching foreign languages allows you to reproduce learning situations, helps to complement traditional teaching methods, contributes to the formation of fundamental skills of foreign language communication from the realization of the possibility of expressing thoughts in another language to the independent solution of communication problems, increases the desire, interest of students in learning, makes them - take a fresh look at the subjects being studied, thus revealing their creative and intellectual capabilities, talents.

Currently, the concept of "SMART" is the main purpose of the development of educational systems. The main source of knowledge is electronic, educational Internet content, technological operations are to provide feedback from teachers and students, the exchange of knowledge between them.

Smart education is a concept that involves a comprehensive modernization of all educational processes, as well as the methods and technologies used in these processes.

SMART education is capable of providing a high level of learning that meets the challenges and opportunities of today's world, will allow young people to adapt in a rapidly changing, unstable environment, and will ensure the transition from book

content to active content using a single common repository of educational materials with an analytical search system. The quality of educational materials in the repository should be constantly monitored through the introduction of various materials and work in conjunction with educational process management systems.

Considering the current, innovative technologies, one should dwell in more detail on the topic of using Internet resources in teaching a foreign language. The possibilities of using online resources are enormous.

With the help of web resources, you can perform the following tasks:

- include network materials in the content of the lesson;
- carry out an independent search for information by students as part of the work on the project;
- to organize and develop reading skills using materials from the network of any degree of complexity;
- improve listening skills based on audio texts from a network of online resources;
- replenish the vocabulary with vocabulary, abbreviations of the modern foreign language;
- study the culture of a particular language.

So, for example, a teacher of German at the ChSPU named after I.Ya. Yakovleva M. G. Alekseeva actively uses the site “die deutsche welle” in her work with students. As a rule, this site is very useful in independent work. It is a free German course suitable for both beginners and advanced users. The site offers a wide range of audio texts, videos, various levels of difficulty. This skill can be used in your lessons and school teachers of the German language. The advantage of the site is that it is simple and easy to use, which is why it is one of the best platforms for learning a language. In order to interest the listener, it offers famous talk shows, music videos, funny videos with hidden meanings, news, fascinating dialogues, etc. With the help of exercises that are also available on this site, you can test your knowledge of German grammar and vocabulary to identify your weaknesses. I would like to give an example of working with audio texts from the site “die deutsche Welle”, which we enter quite often to complete various tasks in the German

language. The recording of many texts lasts only 2 minutes, and this contributes to the fact that the listener does not get tired during this time, his attention does not dissipate and interest does not disappear. One of the themes is called "Viele Köche verderben den Brei". This is a German proverb, which is translated into Russian as "Seven nannies have a child without an eye." At the beginning of the entry, the author describes the meaning of the proverb in several sentences. For example, he says: "Alleine arbeitet man manchmal am besten. Denn wenn viele Menschen mit unterschiedlichen Meinungen und Methoden zusammen etwas machen wollen, kann das zu Schwierigkeiten führen." First, the work is carried out on an individual basis.

Everyone listens on their own. As experience shows, various difficulties arise in collective listening. After that, the author begins the story. While listening, students take notes. Recording is allowed to listen 2-3 times. When listening for the first time, it is necessary to pay attention to the speed of the speaker's speech, his intonation, and try to understand the general meaning of the text. At the second listening, they record: "Who? Where? When? What did you do?". If the text is found or the speaker's speech is very fast, it is recommended to listen three times. After this, the teacher asks questions like "richtig oder falsch", how well the students have mastered the text. Further increased work in pairs. Students must retell the text to each interlocutor, ask and resolve questions on the content. Thus, the ability to work in pairs is developed, which develops the development of dialogue speech.

But this site also has long audio recordings from 11 to 19 minutes, which are best listened to outside the classroom, for example, at home. Working outside the classroom forms the skill of independent work. For example, on the topic "Lernen an der Universität" the text lasts 9 minutes and the speaker's speech in this audio text is very fast. But the topic is very useful and has practical value for schoolchildren and students, because the announcer gives advice on studying: "How to prepare for exams?", "How to use the electronic library?", "Where to look for material?" etc.

Since students usually do this work at home, they can listen to the texts many times until they understand and extract the necessary information. Usually everyone

gets an individual task to test understanding after listening. Tasks can be such as preparing private questions, correct and incorrect statements, printing text with errors or text with gaps, so the student must listen to the audio text carefully and write down every word so as not to miss important things. The advantage of working with "die deutsche Welle" is that the teacher can alternate audio texts from easy to difficult. For example, during the week they listen to simple and fairly short texts lasting 1-2 minutes, and before the weekend they give a recording of an average level so that the student has enough time to listen to long material and write down the most important points in order to discuss them with the teacher after the weekend in the classroom.

30 years ago, it was impossible to imagine that you can listen to a native speaker in real time, but today, thanks to new innovative technologies, we are given this opportunity, which makes learning a foreign language many times easier and much more interesting.

Thus, at present it is impossible to imagine the educational process without the use of innovative pedagogical technologies. Such technologies are firmly established in the modern education system. Today, a foreign language teacher has a lot of opportunities, which helps to conduct their classes more interesting, more informative. These opportunities encourage students to be more active. Compared with the traditional method of teaching, new implementations in teaching inevitably change the role of the teacher. Its task is to increase the independent work of students, support in the development of the individual. Such training allows you to increase motivation for learning, significantly increases interest in learning, and also gives good results in the formation of communication skills compared to the traditional method.

LITERATURE

1. Nazarova N. B., Mokhova O. L. New information technologies in teaching foreign languages // Modern problems of science and education. 2016. No. 3.
2. Application of SMART technologies in the educational process "Education without borders". MBOU "Secondary School No. 1". 2015. 20 p. [Electronic resource]. Access mode: <https://infourok.ru/primenenie-smarttehnologii-v-obrazovatelnom-processe-mobu-soshobrazovanie-bez-granic-540134.html>
3. Sargsyan A. V. Use of Internet resources in a foreign language lesson [Electronic resource]. Access mode: <https://nsportal.ru/shkola/inostrannye42-yazyki/library/2016/02/23/ispolzovanie-internet-resursov-na-uroke-inostrannogo>
4. Kizlyakova E. S. Introduction of the latest information technologies in teaching foreign languages. S.-P., 2010. 11 p.